

**DEVELOPMENT TRANSLATION OF INTERNATIONAL LAW NORMS
THROUGH CONTENT-BASED**

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Abstract:

This research work is devoted to the features of the translation of legal terminology from English into Uzbek. The need for professional translation today manifests itself in all spheres of life.

Key words: law, international law, legal terms, lexical units, translation, terminology, legalization, contract, documents, dictionary, proficiency, comparison.

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Among the many complex problems studied by modern linguistics, an important place is occupied by the problem of linguistic aspects of interlingual speech activity, which is called "translation" or "translation activity". From the very beginning, translation performed an important social function, which made possible inter-lingual communication between people. The widespread dissemination of written translations gave people access to the cultural achievements of other peoples, made it possible for interaction and mutual enrichment of cultures and literatures.

Any serious business activity can be achieved through contracts and agreements. The written form ensures that different people, such as buyers and sellers, interact in accordance with a particular business strategy and their interests are taken into account by their partners. One of the most popular types of translation today is the translation of documents. The documents are divided into two main groups: documents of individuals; Translation of legal entities' documents is becoming increasingly relevant in today's global economy. One of the peculiarities of translating the documents of individuals is the need to give them legal force, their legalization for presentation outside the country.

The object of the study is scientific and technical terminology and multi-component terms. The subject of the study is the peculiarities and complexity of translation of scientific texts in general, and terminology in particular. As for the purpose of the work, it can be defined as identifying the difficulties encountered in translating scientific and technical terminology. Moreover, one of the objectives is also to create an electronic dictionary that could include multi-component terminology applicable in narrower, little-studied areas of knowledge.

The theoretical significance of my work is due to the importance of research and study of the specifics of translation of scientific and technical terminology. As for practical significance, it is that in one way or another sometimes the translator has to deal with scientific terms, and with it the difficulties of technical translation, without knowledge of which you can make many mistakes, even a

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good foreign language. In this regard, this research can be a good guide to translating terms of varying degrees of complexity.

The scientific novelty of my diploma work is that due to technological progress, more and more terms appear every day in different fields of knowledge and the need to develop a clear algorithm for translation of scientific terminology is growing. Moreover, multi-component terms have not previously been considered in the texts of scientific and technical literature in such detail that once again confirms the need to develop a clear algorithm for their translation. Our research work is aimed at identifying difficulties in translating scientific and technical terminology from Uzbek to English. The introduction of basic concepts of economic and state relations between different countries, the continuous development of science and technology, as well as modern technologies in various industries and fields of activity increase the importance of the foreign language, which acts as a "bridge" between representatives of different cultures and languages.

There are many definitions. V. N. Commissioners defines translation as a type of language mediation, which is entirely oriented towards the foreign-language original. If we mean translation from one language to another, then the translation can be considered as a process and as a result. The Scottish linguist John Catford, who is the founder of the theoretical concept of translation, argues that translation is the replacement of textual material in one language (IA) with equivalent textual material on another. On the basis of this definition, it can be concluded that the main problem with translation is the establishment of the nature and conditions of translation equivalence.

In this article we are dealing with the translation of texts of scientific technical style. In this regard, it is necessary to find out what style is, what are the texts of this subject and what features have. Language style is a collection of language tools. The style of non-fiction, in turn, differs by the presence of special characteristics. The scientific and technical texts use special terms that are selected in accordance with the area of knowledge to which a text refers to accurately conveys thought. As for grammar, scientific and technical texts abound with the use of passive, impersonal and vaguely personal designs. Most of the sentences are complex and complex.

Consequently, alliances, composite pretexts and various revolutions are widely used in the language of scientific and technical style. In addition, it is worth noting that the author of the text, trying to convey information and explain certain facts, discoveries, processes, avoids personal forms of verb, replacing them with a suffering pledge. In this regard, it becomes clear that all processes and phenomena in the text act as subject, eclipsing the author of the text. The style of presentation of information. Due to the rapid development of modern technologies, the translation of scientific technical terminology is especially relevant in recent times. Today, scientific and technical translation is not only a form of translation, but also a separate applied discipline. A distinctive feature of scientific and technical texts is the abundance of terms and various phrases, formulas, graphs, the translation of which can cause a number of difficulties. And the main task of scientific and technical translation is a brief and accurate presentation of information and the absence of any emotional coloring.

The group of documents of legal entities, the translation of which has its own peculiarities and most often causes difficulties, include contracts, contracts and insurance documents. It should be noted that translation theory often requires a full understanding of the translator's source code. But by making

such demands, the authors do not specify how it is possible to achieve a full understanding, which causes a negative reaction in translators. The translator can acquire the knowledge he needs in many different ways. At the disposal of the translator are intelligent and bilingual dictionaries, glossaries, databases, information-search thesaurus, encyclopedias, texts, legislation, regulations, personal contacts with specialists, etc. can certainly be useful to the translator. But the organization of search is crucial. The sequence, for example, can be such. When the language units in the text are difficult to understand, the translator turns to the dictionaries to determine whether the language unit is compliant with the concept. [6, p.124].

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